

Endodontic Disinfection Using Photodynamic Theory Investing The Effectiveness of PDT As An Adjunct to Conventional Irrigation Systems For Root Canal Disinfection

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Introduction

Efficient root canal disinfection is basics to successful endodontic treatment and is currently focused on mechanical debridement using nickel-titanium (NiTi) rotary file systems, irrigation using antimicrobial agents such as sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl), and inter appointment dressings^[1]. Despite the improvement in the efficiency of NiTi system, studies that compare between rotary and hand instruments showed no significant difference in bacterial reduction. NaOCl remains the “gold standard” due to its antibacterial and tissue dissolving traits, but bacterial eradication is not uniformly attainable with any available method.^[2] Moreover, 40% to 60% of root canals contain viable bacteria even after chemomechanical preparation with antimicrobial irrigants in place.^[3] Calcium hydroxide dressing between appointments has been demonstrated to increase the removal of bacteria.^[1]

Apical periodontitis, a bacterial infection of the root canal system, demands a drop in intracanal bacterial populations for therapy to be successful. Although it is desirable to eliminate bacteria totally, the current objective is merely to diminish the population of bacteria to levels compatible with healing of periradicular tissues.^[4] This is the basis of the debate over if RCT should be performed in one or two visits, and protocols that can effectively disinfect the root canal in a single visit are a key area of interest. The potential of laser technologies, including PDT, to speed up disinfection while maintaining efficacy offers promise in this regard. For better disinfection, new techniques like laser therapies, hydraulic, sonic, and ultrasonic irrigation, gaseous ozone, and photodynamic therapy (PDT) have been studied.^[2]

The use of nontoxic photosensitizer PDT, which, with a specific wavelength of light in the presence of oxygen, activates reactive

oxygen species that could eradicate bacteria. Evidence exists that PDT has more antibacterial potential and has been proposed as an supplement to conventional endodontic disinfection protocols.^[3] In vitro, ex vivo, and in vivo studies demonstrated PDT's effectiveness in reducing the bacterial load, mainly against *Enterococcus faecalis*. It is, however, unexplored to what extent PDT may be effective in supplementing chemomechanical preparation in comparison between commonly used photosensitizers such as methylene blue and toluidine blue.^[3]

Photodynamic Therapy (PDT) in Endodontics

Mechanism of PDT

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) is a two-stage treatment process involving the application of a photosensitizing (PS) compound to target tissues, followed by activation through exposure to visible light of a specific wavelength. In the first stage, the PS compound is applied and retained within the target tissues.^[5] It undergoes a light-activating process where the light used might be directly targeted at the targeted area or transmitted to more inner tissues. Upon being exposed to light, PS transitions from its ground state to an excited triplet state.^[6] Activation of the sensitizer in the presence of oxygen results in two types of chemical reactions with biomolecules. Type I reactions include electron or hydrogen abstraction, resulting in the production of free radicals. In combination with oxygen, these reactive species produce highly reactive oxygen^[7]

Type I reactions can lead to direct cellular damage through the effects of free radicals.^[8] On the other hand, type II reactions produce

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singlet oxygen, an electronically excited and very reactive oxygen species, which is the primary mechanism responsible for microbial cell destruction. While it is difficult to differentiate between the two kinds of reactions, both may occur, and the equilibrium is determined by variables such as oxygen tension and PS concentration.^[9]

This can create oxidative stress in the targeted region, which may potentially harm the target cells.^[10] There are two major mechanisms associated with the bactericidal activity of PDT: the disruption of the plasma membrane and/or DNA of the cell, which causes death to the cell.^{[11][12]} Cellular damage ensues when ROS overwhelm the cell's biochemical defense mechanisms by oxidizing cellular components, such as membranes and DNA, ultimately leading to death of the cell (Konopka & Goslinski, 2007).^[9] From a clinical standpoint, PDT is both cytotoxic and vasculotoxic (Babilas et al., 2010).^[13]

Additionally, PDT can cause damage to the bacterial cytoplasmic membrane through the generation of cytotoxic species, which have effects on membrane transport systems, inhibit enzyme activities, and cause lipid peroxidation, among other effects (Takasaki et al., 2009).^[12] Singlet oxygen species can efficiently kill a vast range of microbes eg bacteria, fungi, viruses, and protozoa.^[12]

Photosensitizers Used in Endodontic

Many natural and synthetic photoactive compounds have "photosensitizing potential." Nonetheless, to be effective microbicides, the most powerful photosensitizers must come from groups such as the halogenated xanthenes, phenothiazines, acridines, and formed chlorines. Ideally, the photosensitizer should not be toxic and cause any side effects, not be mutagenic, selectively accumulate in the target tissue, be easy to administer, be inexpensive, have a high light absorption efficiency, and have an efficient energy transfer to ground-state oxygen.^[14] Moreover, the quantum yield should be high, the state lifetimes long, and the efficiency should be high.^[15]

PDT in RCT has been validated with various combinations of photosensitizers and light sources, and the results have been inconsistent.^[14] Even when the same photosensitizer and light source are used, differences in illumination protocols, photosensitizer concentrations, light exposure time, and intensity make comparisons difficult. Some of the critical groups of photosensitizers used in PDT comprise these that absorb light at ranges 621-651 nm, phenothiazines (621-701 nm), cyanines (601-804 nm), phytotherapy agents (551-701 nm), and phthalocyanines (661-701 nm).^[16] Some widely explored and used dyes during PDT are phenothiazines such as methylene blue and Toluidine blue O. Even, curcumin present primarily in turmeric was in recent times investigated by researchers in dentistry also as a photosensitizer agent for PDT.^[17]

Studies show that methylene blue has a maximum absorption peak at 660 nm, while Toluidine blue O absorbs at 630 nm. Both have similar bactericidal effects and can inactivate both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. The choice of photosensitizers in dentistry depends on the light source used. For effective PDT, photosensitizers typically require the longest wavelength

possible and adequate light intensity at that wavelength. The commonly used light sources fall within the wavelengths of 634 to 806 nm and include helium-neon lasers, 638 nm; gallium-aluminum-arsenide diode lasers, 620-677 nm; and argon lasers, 485-524 nm.^[18]

The common clinical PDT light sources include lasers, LEDs, and incandescent lights. The most preferred PDT light source is the diode laser, which is easy to handle, relatively inexpensive, and portable. Laser light has many advantages such as it can be delivered through fiber optics, is very efficient, monochromatic, and high intensity.^[19] They are costly. Non-laser sources like LEDs are increasingly used for illuminating easily accessible tissue surfaces. Incandescent lights are advantageous because they can be filtered to match the absorption characteristics of any photosensitizer but are less efficient when coupled with optical fibers or liquid light guides, leading to heat generation and reduced output.^[16]

From a perspective of bacterial and photosensitizer interaction, three major factors relate the effectiveness of PDT: (i) the ability of the photosensitizer to interact with the bacterial membrane, (ii) its ability to penetrate and act within the bacterial cell, and (iii) the generation of singlet oxygen around the bacterial cell upon light activation.^[19] The more structural differences in outer membranes between Gram-negative bacteria limit their susceptibility to the effectiveness of killing by PDT based on hydrophobic as well as charge interaction factors on a photosensitizer. Charges may also play a significant role, depending on the bacterial surface and the photosensitizing agent used: more cationic drugs being capable of inactivating both Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative bacteria due to methylene blue, Toluidine blue O.^[20]

Generally, Gram-negative bacteria are less susceptible to photosensitizers commonly used in PDT because of their impermeable peptidoglycan layer and the acid pH of the outer cytoplasmic membrane. Gram-positive species are more permeable and can allow the photosensitizer to diffuse inside the cell. There are also claims of bacterial inactivation due to the failure of penetration of the photosensitizer into the cells.^[21] From various studies, damage to critical structures can be caused even if sufficient singlet oxygen is produced near the bacterial membrane. The proximity of the photosensitizer's reactive oxygen species to the bacteria would suffice for effective PDT, without which direct contact with the photosensitizer and bacteria might not be required. Such challenging locations could also lead to effective treatment without such direct interaction between the photosensitizer and bacteria. Therefore, it could be essential to the effectiveness of PDT to access more inaccessible areas.^[22]

Photodynamic therapy is thus deemed a type II mechanism in which singlet oxygen serves as the active species causing cell damage.^[21]

Challenges in Root Canal Disinfection

Anatomical Complexity:

Anatomical complexities in root canal systems, such as curvatures, isthmuses, lateral canals, and irregular shapes (e.g., C-shaped, oval, or flattened canals), create significant challenges during endodontic treatment. These structures make it difficult

for instruments to reach all areas of the canal, especially smaller or more intricate spaces. As a result, some regions of the canal may remain untreated, leading to insufficient cleaning and disinfection.^[23]

Even when treatment follows acceptable standards, these anatomical features can prevent full bacterial reduction. Bacteria may persist in areas that are hard to access with conventional instruments, which contributes to a higher risk of post-treatment apical periodontitis. Consequently, the complexity of root canal anatomy plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of endodontic procedures and the risk of persistent infection.^[24]

Endodontic Biofilm

Endodontic biofilms play a significant role in therapeutic challenges as they represent a primary survival strategy for bacteria, particularly during periods of starvation. These biofilms are a major contributor to endodontic treatment failures due to their ability to protect bacterial colonies in several ways. First, biofilms provide a protective barrier against the external environment, allowing bacteria to survive hostile conditions. Additionally, they facilitate the entrapment of nutrients, supporting the growth of microbial communities. The biofilm also creates a secure environment for genetic exchange among bacterial species, contributing to their adaptability. Furthermore, the biofilm's structure offers inherent resistance to antimicrobial agents, including endodontic irrigants and intracanal medicaments.^[25]

The antimicrobial resistance of biofilms is a significant clinical concern, as they possess several characteristics that make them highly resilient to treatment. One such feature is the slow penetration of antimicrobial agents due to the polysaccharide matrix (extracellular polymeric substance, or EPS) that impedes the diffusion of these agents.^[26] Biofilms also exhibit enhanced tolerance to antimicrobials because of a higher density of cells, including persister cells that are dormant and resistant to treatment. The arrangement of cells within the biofilm further protects the microorganisms at its core, as they are shielded from medications that primarily target cells at the periphery. Additionally, the reduced growth rate and lower nutritional requirements of the cells within the biofilm contribute to their resistance, making the treatment of these infections more challenging.^[27]

Effectiveness of PDT

There are many relevant studies regarding the use of photodynamic therapy (PDT) in endodontics. Several studies have explored its potential as an adjunct to conventional root canal treatments, showing that PDT can significantly reduce bacterial loads.

The study by Firmino, R^[29] evaluates the effectiveness of photodynamic therapy (PDT) as a support to conventional endodontic treatment, highlighting its ability to significantly reduce microorganisms and promote periapical healing. The use of PDT, combined with a diode laser and methylene blue as the photosensitizing agent, resulted in faster periapical repair compared to traditional treatments, with bone formation and periodontal ligament restructuring observed as early as six months. PDT's advantages include its non-thermal effects on periapical tissues, making it a safer option compared to high-power lasers. However, factors such as photosensitizer penetration, light deli-

very systems, and energy doses require further research to standardize protocols for optimal results. Overall, PDT offers a cost-effective, easy-to-implement alternative that enhances conventional endodontic treatments, leading to quicker recovery and improved clinical outcomes.

A study by Miranda^[30] evaluated the ex vivo antimicrobial effectiveness of the EndoVac irrigation system combined with PDT, chemomechanical debridement, and intracanal calcium hydroxide (CaOH₂) in treating root canal infections caused by *Enterococcus faecalis*. The study found that while all protocols significantly reduced bacterial levels, PDT did not provide additional antimicrobial benefits beyond conventional chemomechanical debridement and intracanal medication. The use of methylene blue as the photosensitizer, combined with specific concentrations and irradiation times, was effective in reducing *E. faecalis* levels. However, the limited penetration of PDT into biofilms within dentinal tubules, low oxygen availability, and ineffective photosensitizer delivery may have contributed to the modest results. Intracanal medication showed a modest but beneficial reduction in bacterial counts, emphasizing its role in controlling residual bacteria. Despite the reduction in microbial load, total elimination of bacteria was not achieved, likely due to the persistence of *E. faecalis* in complex canal structures.

In a study Rios A^[31] evaluates the effectiveness of photodynamic therapy (PDT) with LED light and TBO (Toluidine Blue O) as an adjunctive antimicrobial treatment for root canal disinfection, particularly against *E. faecalis* biofilms. *E. faecalis* biofilms were allowed to develop in root canals for two weeks, simulating clinical conditions. The results show that PDT with LED light significantly reduced the survival rate of *E. faecalis*, with a survival rate of 2.9% after 30 seconds of PDT. When combined with NaOCl irrigation, the survival rate dropped further to 0.1%. These findings suggest that PDT with TBO and LED light can significantly enhance bacterial reduction in the root canal system compared to traditional disinfection methods. The study also observed that TBO alone and LED light alone reduced bacterial survival, but the combination with NaOCl was most effective. The study concludes that PDT could serve as an effective adjunct to conventional root canal treatments, though further clinical studies are necessary to confirm these in vitro results.

The study by Silva^[32] investigates the effectiveness of adjunctive antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT) in endodontic treatment for teeth with apical periodontitis, where infection is present in both the root canal and periapical tissues. The results demonstrate that aPDT significantly reduced inflammatory cells, with moderate fibrogenesis and neoangiogenesis observed in the treated groups. These findings suggest that aPDT can promote tissue healing and reduce inflammation in the periapical region. However, despite the absence of inflammatory cells, the healing process was still in the early stages after 90 days, likely due to the potential extrusion of photosensitizer into the periapical area, which may have caused mild toxicity to host cells. While previous studies show aPDT's potential in treating periodontal diseases without damaging host cells, the current study indicates that the parameters used for aPDT might not be

optimal for complete periapical healing. The study highlights the need for further research to determine the ideal aPDT parameters and the therapeutic window that can effectively eliminate bacteria without harming healthy tissue, suggesting that aPDT could be a promising adjunct to conventional root canal treatment for apical periodontitis.

Another study by Samiei M et al^[33] compared the antibacterial effects of photo-activated low-level lasers (PAD), 2% chlorhexidine (CHX), and 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) on *Enterococcus faecalis* in infected root canals. The results showed that all three agents significantly reduced bacterial counts compared to the control group, with no significant difference between PAD and 2% CHX. However, 2.5% NaOCl proved to be the most effective, demonstrating superior antibacterial efficacy. While PAD alone showed some effectiveness, it was less potent than NaOCl, though it did contribute to the reduction of *E. faecalis* in complex root canal areas. The study suggests that further research is needed to evaluate the most effective disinfection protocols in vivo, particularly for diverse bacterial species in root canals.

Study by Meire, M. A^[34] investigated the effectiveness of Nd:YAG, KTP lasers, and photo-activated disinfection (PAD) in eliminating *Enterococcus faecalis* in both in vitro and ex vivo root canal models, comparing them to sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) as a control. The results showed that neither the Nd:YAG nor KTP lasers effectively reduced the viability of planktonic *E. faecalis* cells, likely due to poor absorption of the laser wavelengths by water. PAD, despite methodological issues, resulted in a significant reduction of bacterial counts in vitro, but its effect was less pronounced in the ex vivo model. NaOCl, while showing the most effective results in vitro with a 100% bacterial kill, demonstrated only a 2-log reduction in the infected tooth model, likely due to inactivation by organic material in the root canal. Overall, while lasers did not provide clinically relevant reductions in bacterial load, NaOCl showed some effectiveness, but all treatments were limited in eradicating infections, especially in areas difficult to access in the root canal. The study concluded that more research, including randomized clinical trials and the exploration of different laser settings, is needed to improve root canal disinfection protocols.

One study by Nunes MR, Mello^[35] investigated the potential of photodynamic therapy (PDT) as an antimicrobial treatment for infected root canals, comparing its effectiveness to traditional sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) irrigation. The results showed that PDT significantly reduced the microbial load (99.41% to 99.65%) in root canals, but NaOCl provided higher reductions (99.99%). While PDT's effectiveness improved with longer irradiation times, higher energy doses, and appropriate photosensitizer concentrations (such as methylene blue, MB), the use of conventional optical fibers did not significantly enhance the antimicrobial effect. Despite high reductions in *E. faecalis* populations, PDT did not achieve total bacterial elimination, likely due to limited oxygen availability in the root canal and the complexity of dentinal tubule penetration. The study concluded that while PDT shows promise, further research is needed to optimize its parameters and address the challenges of achieving complete disinfection.

One of the review assessed the methodological quality of in vitro studies comparing photodynamic therapy (PDT) and sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) in reducing *E. faecalis* in root canals, highlighting the lack of standardized parameters for clinical PDT application in endodontics. The review identified significant methodological variations among the studies, such as differences in root canal instrumentation, NaOCl concentrations and exposure times, and the use of photosensitizers like methylene blue (MB) and toluidine blue (TB). While PDT demonstrated effectiveness, its antimicrobial impact was enhanced when combined with NaOCl, yielding better results than conventional treatments alone. However, the lack of consistency in PDT parameters (e.g., laser power, photosensitizer concentration, and exposure time) hindered comparisons and meta-analysis, underlining the need for further studies to establish standardized protocols for PDT in clinical endodontics. The review concluded that PDT could be a valuable adjunctive treatment in endodontic disinfection but requires more research to optimize its application.

A study done by Muhammad^[36] evaluated the efficacy of Photodynamic Therapy (PDT) in combination with ultrasonic irrigation for treating microbial biofilms in root canals, specifically targeting *E. faecalis*. The researchers compared two PDT methods—using a 650 nm diode laser and LED light—against ultrasonic irrigation using sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) and EDTA. PDT was used as an adjunct to conventional root canal treatment, performed after chemo-mechanical debridement to target biofilm remnants. The study found that while PDT reduced bacterial colonies, its effectiveness was not as strong as ultrasonic irrigation, which demonstrated superior results in removing biofilm due to acoustic streaming. The study also highlighted the challenge of biofilm resistance, particularly from *E. faecalis*, and discussed the limitations of PDT, including the potential for incomplete bacterial elimination and the need for additional techniques like real-time PCR or FISH for more accurate bacterial assessment. Ultrasonic irrigation proved to be more time-efficient and cost-effective, making it a preferred method in clinical practice.

PDT Against Resistant And Complex Cases

Several studies have explored its potential as an adjunct to conventional root canal treatments, showing that PDT can significantly reduce bacterial loads, particularly *Enterococcus faecalis*, and promote tissue healing in periapical areas.

Study by Asnaashari M^[28] investigates the effectiveness of antimicrobial photodynamic therapy (aPDT) compared to calcium hydroxide in disinfection of root canals, particularly against *E. faecalis*, a common pathogen in refractory infections. While both treatments reduced bacterial load, aPDT demonstrated superior efficacy in eliminating *E. faecalis*. The study employed a randomized design to minimize bias and used both biofilm and planktonic bacteria samples. It highlights the advantages of aPDT, especially with LED light, which is safer and more cost-effective than high-power lasers. The results suggest that aPDT could be a promising alternative for root canal disinfection, but further research is necessary to optimize protocols and confirm its role in routine clinical practice.

The study by^[37] Garcez, A. S., demonstrated the effectiveness of Photodynamic Therapy (PDT) as an adjunct to conventional endodontic surgery for reducing bacterial load in periapical lesions, including drug-resistant infections. PDT achieved a significant reduction in microbial contamination without contributing to microbial resistance, making it a safer and more effective alternative to long-term antibiotic use. The study found that PDT, when combined with mechanical debridement, provided superior microbial reduction compared to conventional treatments, and the surrounding tissue was not harmed. After 36 months, all patients were asymptomatic, and the treated teeth regained normal function. The results suggest that PDT can enhance the outcomes of endodontic surgery by providing additional microbial decontamination and improving the healing of periapical lesions without cytotoxic effects.^[37]

These findings collectively suggest that while PDT offers a promising alternative or adjunct to traditional endodontic therapies, further research is needed to optimize its protocols and address its limitations in achieving full bacterial eradication.

Challenges and Limitations of PDT

- **Access to Light**

1. The effectiveness of PDT is dependent on the light source used, which should match the activation spectrum of the photosensitizer (PS). The light sources used in PDT include lasers and light-emitting diodes (LEDs) with wavelengths typically between 630-800 nm^[17,20].
2. **Laser and LED Use:** Low power lasers are most commonly used in PDT due to their high efficiency, portability, and ability to focus light precisely through fiber optics. Diode lasers are particularly favored due to their ease of handling and lower cost^[20].
3. **Thermal Side Effects and Alternatives:** Lasers concentrate energy in a small area, which can induce thermal injury, while LEDs avoid this issue, making them safer for surrounding tissues^[38]. LED light sources are suggested to minimize temperature rise while still providing effective energy delivery for PDT^[20].

- **Optimal Photosensitizer Selection**

1. The selection of a PS is crucial for PDT efficacy. Factors like phototoxicity, absorption wavelengths, and ability to penetrate bacterial membranes affect the choice. Methylene blue (MB) and Toluidine Blue O (TBO) are frequently studied for their effectiveness in deactivating both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria^[20].
2. The PS should have high absorption in the light wavelength used and must generate singlet oxygen effectively^[39]. Cationic PSs, like MB and TBO, are effective against a range of bacterial species^[9].

- **Toxicity and Safety**

1. PDT is generally safe within the therapeutic window, with studies showing lower cytotoxicity compared to traditional endodontic irrigants like NaOCl^[29]. Curcumin, for example, has been used as a non-cytotoxic PS in dental applications^[29].

- **Cost**

1. **Cost of Light Sources:** While diode lasers are more affordable and portable compared to other lasers, they can still be relatively costly compared to LED or halogen lamps, which are cheaper but less efficient^[20].

2. **Ease of Use:** Diode lasers, being portable and user-friendly, have become the preferred light source for PDT^[40].

- **Practical Concerns with PS and Light Sources**

1. The practical use of PDT in clinical settings requires careful consideration of the PS's toxicity, the light source's intensity, and the treatment's safety profile^[41]. The potential for tissue damage due to thermal effects requires caution when using high-intensity light sources^[12].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the studies reviewed demonstrate that photodynamic therapy (PDT) has significant potential as an adjunct to conventional endodontic treatments, offering benefits such as enhanced microbial reduction and improved periapical healing. While PDT has shown promising results in reducing bacterial loads, especially *Enterococcus faecalis*, its effectiveness can vary depending on factors such as the photosensitizer used, light delivery systems, and energy doses. Several studies have highlighted PDT's advantages, such as its non-thermal effects on periapical tissues, which make it a safer alternative to high-power lasers. However, challenges such as limited penetration into dentinal tubules, oxygen availability, and incomplete bacterial elimination remain. While PDT may not achieve total bacterial eradication on its own, its combination with other disinfection protocols, like sodium hypochlorite, has proven to yield better outcomes. Despite these promising results, further research is necessary to standardize PDT protocols, optimize its application in clinical practice, and address the limitations that prevent it from being a complete solution for root canal disinfection. Overall, PDT appears to be a valuable adjunct in endodontic therapy, with the potential for improved clinical outcomes when integrated into comprehensive treatment regimens.

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